

Alignment of maSMP metadata schema to RSMD

Project ID: OC-RSMD-11

Leyla Jael Castro, Dhvani Solanki

From Data to Software Management Plans

maSMP schema aligned to RSMD

- Initial status: Current [maSMPs types and properties](#) and corresponding [usage profiles](#)
- Approach: maSMP properties mapping to RSMD guideline available [here](#).
- Results: Planned updated version of maSMP metadata schema with results from the alignment to the RSMD guidelines → New metadata terms identified

Challenges

- Same metadata properties could be aligned to multiple RSMD guidelines
- Practical realization of maSMPs and RSDM guidelines
 - We need/want good metadata
 - We need to make it easier for researchers to automate the metadata extraction/creation process